

MCNP Geometry Agnostic Predictive Modeling Framework for Pulse Reactor Spatiotemporal Delayed Gamma Energy Deposition to an Experiment Target

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ABSTRACT

Pulse reactor predictive modeling requires time-dependent estimates of energy deposition in experiment targets. Current MCNP-based workflows obtain time-integrated target heating from prompt neutrons, delayed neutrons, and prompt gammas, then apply a characteristic pulse power history and total pulse energy to construct the time-dependent response. This approach is fast and often agrees well near the prompt peak, but omission of delayed-gamma heating can cause divergence at post-pulse times (e.g., >1 s). Delayed gammas are commonly addressed by coupling MCNP to depletion/activation tools (e.g., ORIGEN or CINDER) to generate time-dependent photon sources. This work instead leverages MCNP's built-in delayed-gamma capability to capture delayed-gamma heating without external code coupling. The method was applied to an Annular Core Research Reactor (ACRR) pulse experiment, and predicted adiabatic temperature rise histories were compared against thermocouple measurements and against results computed without delayed gammas. Including delayed gammas improved agreement with the measured post-pulse heating tail relative to the baseline workflow. Future work includes benchmarking against higher-fidelity coupled approaches, integrating thermomechanical modeling to relax the adiabatic assumption, and quantifying sensitivity to current approximations (e.g., peak-reactivity source representation).

Keywords: MCNP, Pulse-Reactor, Delayed-Gamma, Energy-Deposition

1. INTRODUCTION

Pulse reactors are widely used to expose experiment packages to short, intense irradiation environments for materials testing, component qualification, and safety evaluations. For experiment design and post-test interpretation, it is essential to predict the time-dependent energy deposition (heating) in an experiment target due to neutrons and photons produced during and after a reactor pulse. While the prompt portion of the pulse typically dominates the peak temperature rise, delayed radiation—particularly delayed gamma emission from fission products and activation—can contribute significantly to post-pulse heating and influence measured temperature histories at later times.

A common predictive workflow uses Monte Carlo radiation transport to compute time-integrated target heating from neutrons and prompt gammas, which is then mapped onto time using a characteristic pulse power history and total pulse energy. This approach is computationally efficient and often reproduces the prompt temperature rise well, but it generally neglects delayed gamma heating. More comprehensive treatments rely on either coupling radiation transport to depletion solvers [1] or assuming a fission-product delayed gamma energy spectrum [2].

Rather than coupling transport to an external depletion solver or assuming a fixed delayed-gamma spectrum, this method obtains the delayed gamma emission behavior directly from the activation physics included within the code, building on previous work [3]. The approach separates neutron and prompt gamma heating from delayed gamma heating and recombines them to produce a time-dependent estimate of target energy deposition and adiabatic temperature rise. The methodology is implemented using MCNP wrapped in Python and is compared against thermocouple data from pulse experiments at the Annular Core Research Reactor (ACRR), demonstrating improved agreement with measured temperature behavior compared to workflows that omit delayed gammas.

2. METHODOLOGY

The methodology computes time-dependent target heating by calculating the “baseline” energy deposition without delayed gammas and the standalone delayed gamma heating separately and then combining the results. This captures the dominant physical contributors to target heating.

As shown in Figure 1, baseline energy deposition from neutrons (including both prompt and delayed neutrons) and prompt gammas is first obtained as a time-integrated quantity using a reactor configuration representative of peak reactivity. This baseline contribution is mapped onto time using a prescribed pulse power history and total pulse energy. Delayed gamma energy deposition is then computed independently as a function of time following reactor shutdown using built-in delayed gamma physics. This method accounts for delayed gamma emissions from both fission products and activated materials.

The baseline and delayed gamma contributions are summed to obtain the total time-dependent energy deposition in the target, which is converted to an adiabatic temperature rise using cell-specific material heat capacities. Time dependence arises from the applied pulse power history and from explicit modeling of delayed gamma emission following shutdown. A Python wrapper automates the method.

Sections 2.1 and 2.2 describe the (1) baseline and (2) delayed gamma components of the methodology, respectively.

Figure 1. Method Overview

2.1. Prompt/Delayed Neutron and Prompt Gamma (“Baseline”) Heating

First, the Python wrapper takes the user-provided MCNP input file and updates the control rod heights based on user-defined values. These values (which may be either predicted or measured) should correspond to the maximum reactivity configuration of the pulse reactor. This spatial configuration is where most fission occurs and thus will be used to represent the fission distribution for both Sections 2.1 and 2.2.

To obtain adiabatic temperature rise, Eq (1) will be used where Q/m is the deposited energy per unit mass and c_p is the material-specific heat capacity. The user defines the specific heat capacity so the purpose of MCNP in this method is to calculate the Q/m values for the target of interest.

$$\Delta T = \frac{Q/m}{c_p} \quad (1)$$

To calculate Q/m in MCNP, a +F6 tally is used. In MCNP, a +F6 tally acts as a virtual meter that calculates the total energy deposited (heating) from all particles within a specific volume and time bin

in units of MeV/(g-src) [4]. This value is nearly the desired Q/m , but the result is normalized per source particle (i.e., “src”) meaning it represents the energy from one initial particle and its descendants. To convert from MCNP heating to real-world heating, this value must be multiplied by the number of source particles in the reactor transient (S). To find S , Eq (2) is used where E is pulse energy, ν is the average number of neutrons produced per fission, Q_{fiss} is energy released from fission, and k_{eff} is the effective multiplication factor.

$$S = E \frac{\nu}{Q_{fiss} k_{eff}} \quad (2)$$

The wrapper edits the MCNP input to enable coupled neutron and photon transport. With MCNP defaults, this means that prompt neutrons, delayed neutrons (from fission), and prompt photons are transported. The wrapper then adds in the energy deposition trackers to the user-defined targets of interest. Running this input in MCNP criticality (or KCODE) mode results in obtaining time-integrated energy deposition per source particle. See Reference 4 for more information on MCNP KCODE mode. The number of source particles is then calculated using Eq (2) and multiplied by the MCNP result to obtain Q/m .

The wrapper then generates an energy vs time probability density histogram either by (1) interpolating or extrapolating between reference pulse curves or (2) using a user-defined histogram. This time probability histogram is then used to convert the time-integrated energy deposition to time-dependent energy deposition. Time-dependent adiabatic temperature rise is then calculated using Eq (1).

2.2. Delayed Gamma Heating

Next, delayed-gamma energy deposition is obtained with MCNP. Section 2.2.1 details how the source for MCNP is obtained and Section 2.2.2 details how the produced source is used to find delayed gamma energy deposition.

2.2.1. Fixed-source generation

Per Reference 4, MCNP delayed gamma emission is limited to fixed-source (SDEF) problems. As the name suggests, this problem type requires the user to provide a “fixed-source” which tells MCNP where to spawn particles, what type of particles to spawn, what energy to spawn particles at, and more. See Reference 4 Section 5.8.1 for more information on MCNP source definitions.

For this method, the source is represented by the pulse reactor at the maximum-reactivity state. The particle type is neutrons, the default time distribution is used (i.e., all neutrons are spawned at $t = 0$), a histogram is used for the energy distribution, and (x,y,z) points are used for the spatial distribution.

The MCNP run from Section 2.1 produces what is known as a source tape file. This file is a binary file containing the source particle information (time, energy, position, etc.). Since this run was at the maximum-reactivity state, this source tape file can be parsed to produce the energy and spatial distribution for the fixed-source. The spatial distribution uses uniform sampling of the source tape positions (i.e., all positions equally weighted) and the energy distribution uses the energy values in the source tape to build an 89-group probability histogram (see Figure 6 for energy group structure).

The Python wrapper source tape parsing is modeled after the SRCTP class from the PyNE Nuclear Engineering toolkit for Python and C++ [5].

See Figure 2 for the fixed-source format for this method. This 2-step process with this source effectively assumes the following for delayed gammas:

1. The reactor pulse is instantaneous since all fission source neutrons spawn at $t = 0$.
 - a. In reality, the pulse is quick but not instant, which may lead to non-negligible errors on small ($< 1s$) time scales.
2. All fission source neutrons spawn at the maximum reactivity configuration.
 - a. In reality, the rods are moving throughout the pulse which changes the spatial fission distribution.
3. All delayed gammas are transported through the shutdown reactor configuration.
 - a. In reality, control rods have not inserted by the time early-time delayed gammas are emitted.

```
sdef par=n pos=d1 erg=d2
si1 l x1 y1 z1 ... xn yn zn
sp1 1 ... 1
si2 h e1 ... en
sp2 p1 ... pn
```

Figure 2. Fixed-Source Format

2.2.2. Utilizing fixed-source to capture delayed gamma heating

After obtaining the source for MCNP, 2 fixed-source runs are completed. Both have coupled neutron and photon transport enabled and utilize user-defined rod heights corresponding to the shutdown reactor geometry configuration. One of these runs has delayed gamma emission enabled via the ACT (Section 5.7.3 in Reference 4) option in MCNP while the other does not. The energy deposition from photons can then be calculated in MCNP using the F6:p tally. This is just like the aforementioned +F6 tally except it only measures the energy deposition from photons instead of both photons and neutrons. The wrapper then adds in user-defined time bins to the F6:p tally and runs the calculation.

Because the only difference between these calculations is that one models delayed gammas while the other does not, the delayed-gamma energy-deposition per source particle for each time step i can be obtained by subtraction:

$$E_{dep_{dg,i}} = E_{dep_{dg,on,i}} - E_{dep_{dg,off,i}} \quad (3)$$

Because the delayed gamma temporal behavior is captured natively in the MCNP fixed-source run, the results are simply multiplied by the result in Eq (2) from Section 2.1 to obtain time dependent energy deposition. No time probability histogram scaling is required for this step. Time-dependent adiabatic temperature rise is then calculated using Eq (1).

2.3. The Result

Finally, the wrapper sums the results from Sections 2.1 and 2.2 to obtain the total (prompt neutron, delayed neutron, prompt gamma, and delayed gamma) time-dependent energy deposition and temperature rise for the targets of interest.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The workflow described in Section 2 was applied to an ACRR pulse experiment package and compared against thermocouple (TC) measurements. Section 3.1 provides an overview of the experiment and Section 3.2 applies the method to the experiment and compares modeled results to thermocouple data.

3.1. Experiment Overview

The Annular Core Research Reactor (ACRR) at Sandia National Laboratories is a pulse-capable, pool-type reactor designed for both steady-state and transient testing. Its primary core uses $\text{UO}_2\text{-BeO}$ fuel arranged in an annular configuration surrounding a large central cavity that accommodates diverse experimental setups. The reactor provides variable power and pulse modes for studies of reactor kinetics, energy deposition, radiation transport, and material response under transient conditions.

In February 2024, fuel cell stacks were pulsed at ACRR. This validation focuses on Shot 13577 (from ACRR's shot report, this was a 139.073 MJ pulse), with the stack placed in the CdPoly (cadmium-polyethylene) bucket at the core centerline. Figure 3 shows the experimental setup. Thermocouple data are from the Gen-3 experiment; see Reference [6] for additional experiment details. Figure 4 shows the MCNP fuel cell model used for calculations. The energy-deposition target region corresponds to a ~1 mm Titanium 50A slice at the thermocouple attachment location. The MCNP model is edited from the publicly available model in Reference [7].

Figure 3. Experiment Overview

Figure 4. MCNP Model

Figure 5. Shot 13577 Interpolated Power Curve

3.2. Method Comparison to Thermocouple Data

The following sections describe the method application, the TC data pre-processing steps, and the comparison of method results to TC data.

3.2.1. Method application

All calculations were performed using MCNP6.3.1 with ENDF/B-VIII.0 cross sections [4,8]. A representative pulse power history was constructed (Figure 5) by interpolating/extrapolating ACRR power curves from Shots 13577 and 13578 and scaling the result to match the reported total energy for Shot 13577. This interpolation/extrapolation step was performed as the experimenter will not have access to power history curves before the experiment is performed.

Baseline heating

Since rod positions at the point of maximum reactivity are unknown pre-pulse, the rods were set such that the reactor reactivity was +\$5. Heating results of the +\$5 configuration were compared to results using the actual pulse rod heights and were found to be 4% higher meaning this is a conservative assumption. In the MCNP model, +\$5 corresponded to safety and transient rods fully withdrawn with

control rods inserted 10cm into the core. An MCNP run was performed with coupled neutron and photon transport enabled with a total particle energy-deposition tally (+F6) on target Cell 1101 (i.e., the Titanium 50A “Tally Cell” in Figure 4). This ran with $1E5$ neutrons per cycle for 30 skipped cycles and 130 total cycles.

Time bins used were: [1, 5, 6.64, 8.81, 11.7, 15.5, 20.6, 27.4, 36.4, 48.3, 64.1, 85.1, 113, 150]s. The values used for calculating adiabatic temperature rise ΔT_i for the first time step $\Delta t_0[0 \rightarrow 1s]$ are outlined below in Table I. This process was repeated for each time step yielding the blue “no dg” curve in Figure 7.

Table I: Baseline Calculation Values 0 to 1s

Variable	Value	Source
$\nu \left[\frac{n}{\text{fission}} \right]$	2.433	MCNP
k_{eff}	1.03763	MCNP
$E_{0 \rightarrow 1s} [J]$	1.31×10^8	Python
$Q_{fiss} \left[\frac{\text{MeV}}{\text{fission}} \right]$	192.44	SNL/ACRR
+F6 $\left[\frac{\text{MeV}}{g - src} \right]$	5.9×10^{-6}	MCNP
$c_p \left[\frac{J}{g - K} \right]$	0.523	User Input

The source tape file from this KCODE run was parsed to construct the fixed-source used in the delayed-gamma step. Figure 6 shows the resulting XY spatial distribution and energy histogram.

Figure 6. Fission Neutron Source Position (Left) and Energy (Right) Distribution from Source Tape File

Delayed gamma heating

These distributions were then wrapped into an MCNP fixed-source consistent with Figure 2. Two shutdown-geometry inputs were created and run using $1E6$ source neutrons. Both had control rods fully inserted and similar time-dependent photon energy deposition tallies. The only difference is one had delayed gamma emission enabled via the ACT option in MCNP while the other did not.

The values used for calculating adiabatic temperature rise ΔT_i for time step $\Delta t_0[0 \rightarrow 1s]$ are outlined below in Table II. This process was repeated for each time step and the results for each time bin were summed between “baseline” and “delayed gamma” yielding the orange “no dg+dg” curve in Figure 7.

Table II: Delayed Gamma Calculation Values 0 to 1s

Variable	Value	Source
$E_{Total} [J]$	1.39×10^8	User Input
$E_{dep_{dg_{on},0}} \left[\frac{MeV}{g - src} \right]$	6.01×10^{-5}	MCNP
$E_{dep_{dg_{off},0}} \left[\frac{MeV}{g - src} \right]$	5.89×10^{-5}	MCNP

3.2.2. Thermocouple processing

Three thermocouples (TC1–TC3) were mounted at different locations on the titanium casing. During the pulse, the fuel cell was electrically active, so the thermocouple signals include heating from both the reactor pulse and fuel-cell operation. Because MCNP models only irradiation-induced heating, the fuel-cell contribution was removed using the recorded electrical operating history to isolate the pulse-induced temperature rise, ΔT . The measurements show an immediate post-pulse temperature drop from non-adiabatic heat losses not captured by the adiabatic MCNP assumption; for comparison, this initial drop region was flattened to form an “adiabatic” TC estimate, while the remainder of the trace was left unchanged due to uncertainty between heat-loss effects and measurement noise.

3.2.3. Comparison

Figure 7 compares the method to the processed (“adiabatic”) thermocouple data for Shot 13577. The “no dg” curve omits delayed gammas, while “no dg + dg” adds the delayed-gamma contribution; bands show propagated 1σ MCNP statistical uncertainty. Including delayed gammas improves agreement with both the prompt rise and the delayed heating tail, while late-time temperatures are overpredicted as expected from the adiabatic assumption and unmodeled heat losses. The same workflow was applied to Shot 13578 (342.894 MJ) with the package in the LB-44 bucket and shows the same improvement, indicating the effect is not limited to a single shot. For more information on the CdPoly and LB44 buckets, see References 9 and 10.

Figure 7. Method Results Compared to TC Data from Shot 13577 (Left) and 13578 (Right)

The results obtained were run using 4 nodes on LANL’s high performance computer Rocinante [11]. Overall, the method took 14 min 35 s to run. 1 min 13s of this time was spent running the baseline heating calculation and 13 min 22 s was spent running the delayed gamma heating calculations. Most of the time spent running the delayed-gamma section is from the delayed-gamma enabled calculation because the delayed gamma physics do not allow for OMP threading in MCNP. This is why photonuclear interactions were not included in the calculation as this would mean none of the 3 MCNP calculations could utilize OMP threading. Separate calculations including photonuclear effects obtained decreased heating meaning this omission runs faster and provides a conservative value.

4. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

Including delayed gamma heating (“no dg + dg”) produces substantially better agreement with thermocouple-derived temperature rise histories than the conventional “no dg” approach, improving agreement between both the prompt peak and the post-pulse heating tail. This improvement was consistent across two ACRR shots with different pulse energies and bucket configurations. The Python wrapper automates the method leading to quick turn-around times for analysis on the order of 15 minutes using Rocinante. The method includes many capabilities such as using reference pulse curves for building the time probability histogram which assists with making it a predictive tool.

Future work should prioritize integrating thermomechanical/heat-transfer modeling to move beyond the adiabatic assumption, quantifying sensitivity to key approximations outlined in Section 2.2.1, benchmarking against higher-fidelity alternatives such as MCNP coupled to depletion/activation solvers (e.g., CINDER or ORIGEN-style chains), and applying the method to additional experiment packages and pulse reactors to further establish generality.

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